

**INNOVATION AND EDUCATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT
AND PILOTING OF SMART CARE AND HEALTHCARE
MODELS IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

CZU: [37-048.35 + 001.895]:616-006(478)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6985112

Vasile MUSTEATA¹,
*State University of Medicine and Pharmacy “N. Testemitanu”,
Institute of Oncology*
Veronica CIOBANU²,
Institute of Oncology, Consulting-Diagnostic Center
Diana SIMASCO³,
Institute of Oncology
Veronica FINCIUC⁴,
Institute of Oncology
Cristina DUDNIC⁵,
Institute of Oncology,
Olesea MUSTEATA⁶,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy “N. Testemitanu”

ABSTRACT

Aim of the project: Identification of the innovation and learning means and options for the development of smart care and healthcare in the field of oncology, based on a comprehensive literature review, projection of smart care services through the efficient innovation, collaborative and inclusive education under the D-CARE design within INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme. **Participants:** research and education staff, health and social care providers, informal caretakers, civil society, public administration, economic agents. **Targeted groups** for smart care in Danube region – Republic of Moldova: oncological patients, persons over 55 years of age. **Methods:** An efficient innovation is realized due to cooperative partnerships – triple- and quadruple-helix clusters, which stimulate innovative activity through the intensive interaction. The following potential means will be used within the innovation process: the infrastructure for enabling the development of innovation and knowledge transfer, the knowledge networks and collaboration platforms for supporting continuous improvement, continuous education and training programs for health professionals and other stakeholders working with age-friendly smart care and health care solutions. The development of the Innovative Learning Environments assumes digitization in the field of health – an informational system for monitoring patients in care. We performed also the narrative review of the updated bibliographic sources under the form of a synthesis of the primary studies, dedicated to the innovation and learning. **Results:** The digitization of medicine in the field of oncology allows: the prevention of post-chemotherapy complications and improvement of the complementarity of health services, support of research and development in the field of smart health in the Republic of Moldova; the prevention

¹ **Vasile MUSTEATA**, PhD, MPH, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy “N. Testemitanu”, Institute of Oncology, Department of Hematology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, e-mail: vmusteata@yahoo.co.uk

² **Veronica CIOBANU**, PhD, MPH, Institute of Oncology, Consulting-Diagnostic Center, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, e-mail: chebanu_1971@mail.ru

³ **Diana SIMASCO**, Specialist in Public Institutions, Institute of Oncology, Service of Institutional Coordination, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, e-mail: diana.simasco@gmail.com

⁴ **Veronica FINCIUC**, Institute of Oncology, Department of Hematology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

⁵ **Cristina DUDNIC**, Institute of Oncology, Department of Hematology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

⁶ **Olesea MUSTEATA**, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy “N. Testemitanu”, Department of Odontology, periodontics and oral pathology, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, e-mail: olesea.musteata@usmf.md

of concomitant pathologies and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, by improving the quality of life of citizens and preparing the ground for more efficient ways of organizing and providing healthcare services. The implementation of smart healthcare for elderly oncological patients in the Republic of Moldova is a radical change, which will be embodied in the following: shift of the medical model – from disease-centred care to patient-centred care; shift of the construction of informatization – from clinical informatization to regional medical informatization, which would involve all ecosystems; shift of the medical management – from general management to personalized management; shift of the concept of prevention and treatment of cancer patients – from the focus on the disease treatment to the focus on preventive care. **Conclusions:** Smart healthcare in oncology can facilitate better self-management of health, reduce costs of medical services and researches, ease staff pressure, achieve unified management of materials and information, reduces research time and improves the overall research efficiency.

Keywords: *smart healthcare, oncological patients, innovation, education, triple- and quadruple-helix clusters, Innovative Learning Environments, digitization, management*

Introduction. The need of intelligent (smart) care and health care for oncohematological elderly patients is an eager and increasing public health issue. According to the SWOT analysis, the weaknesses of the care in the elderlies are the shortage of a complex approach and the lack of services that would involve various members of a multidisciplinary team managing addresses of patients in need for smart care and their families. Some of these elderly patients with incurable diseases live alone in their homes in the distant districts of the country, and medical care is provided by the local social workers who visit them 1-2 times a week, that does not ensure a convenient quality of life. The smart healthcare models may serve as an option for the improvement of medical care, especially in elderly patients, and are based on innovative activity and Innovative Learning Environments. Smart healthcare is not just a simple technological advancement, but also an all-round, multi-level changes (Tian S et al, 2019, Liu B.H. et al., 2018). These changes focus on meeting the individual needs of people while improving the efficiency of medical care, which greatly enhances the medical and health service experience, and represent the future development direction of modern medicine. The manuscript starts with the literature review, which describes the current trends of innovation and learning processes, and analyses the current concepts and models of intelligent care and smart healthcare. The Data and Methodology compartment indicates the methodological approaches to the subject under discussion and the methods of data selection and processing. The proposed subject has a practical significance for public health and oncology, because it identifies and summarizes the innovation and learning opportunities, which may be used for implementation of smart healthcare axed on oncological patients. The Model, Findings and Discussion section describes the innovative process and learning within the frame of smart healthcare, being conceptualized under INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme.

Aims of the manuscript: Identification of the innovation and learning means and options for the development of smart care and healthcare in the field of oncology, based on a comprehensive literature review, projection of smart care services through the efficient innovation, collaborative and inclusive education under the D-CARE design within INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme.

1. Literature review. Smart healthcare emerged from the concept of “Smart Planet” proposed by IBM (Armonk, NY, USA) in 2009. Smart Planet is an intelligent infrastructure that uses sensors to perceive information, transmits information through the internet of things, and processes the information using supercomputers and cloud computing (Tian S et al, 2019, Martin J.L. et al, 2010). It can coordinate social systems and integrate them to realize the dynamic and refined management of human society. Smart healthcare is a health service system that uses technology such as portable devices, internet of things, and mobile internet to dynamically access

information, connect different population categories, materials and institutions related to healthcare, and then actively manages and responds to medical ecosystem needs in an intelligent mode. Smart healthcare system can promote interaction between all participants of the healthcare domain, ensure that patients get the services they need, help the parties make informed decisions, and facilitate the rational allocation of resources. Smart healthcare consists of multiple participants, such as doctors and patients, hospitals, and research institutions. It is an organic complex that involves multiple dimensions, including disease prevention and monitoring, diagnosis and treatment, hospital management, health decision-making, and medical researches. The smart healthcare service may be divided into three categories: clinical/scientific research institutions (hospitals, comprehensive cancer centers), regional health decision-making institutions, and individual patient or family users (Tian S et al, 2019, Gagnon M.P. et al, 2016, Redfern J., 2017). In order to improve healthcare system and patients experience the culture should be created, where innovation process can progress, and where the medical staff and patients feel empowered to contribute to the innovation and help make change occur (Kelly C.J., Young A.J., 2017). Healthcare system and its academic institutions-partners commonly lead the world in inventing and testing potential innovations. Innovation can be defined as invention + adoption + diffusion. In healthcare, it may be a new idea, product, service or care pathway that contribute to clear benefits when compared to what is currently performed. Successful innovations often owns two key qualities: usefulness and desirability. For new innovations to progress at scale, access to adequate funding is crucial. There is an increasing number of both public and private funding sources in the European countries, especially in UK, although public funds remain limited (Kelly C.J., Young A.J., 2017). There are following key options that contribute to a culture supporting innovation in UK: best practice tariffs, Innovation Challenge Prizes, healthcare small business research initiatives, Clinical excellence awards, academic health science networks, National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, healthcare innovation portal, innovation scorecard, national innovation accelerator, health and social care innovation expo, healthy new towns programs, continuing clinical innovation points schemes, the innovation technology tariff, clinical entrepreneur programs. Innovations that specifically address one region's local needs are not necessarily a problem, but if they are not joined up across the system they can result in negative consequences. Focusing down too soon may prevent the necessary innovations from being developed. This is the innovation dilemma faced in healthcare system. Offering healthcare professionals high-quality continuous education means leveraging excellence in healthcare performance. Although the educated and adaptable workforce should be a government/business priority, there's a growing lack of experienced and well-trained staff in the healthcare environment in many regions around the globe. To counter this trend, there's a need to raise awareness that education doesn't come to an end once people are in the middle of their professional career. Because the healthcare industry is continuously evolving, technologies considered best practice today can change drastically in just the span of a decade. That's why care providers have to regularly keep up with new techniques and technologies. The innovation process is based on the continuous education and training programs for health professionals in order to insure the development of smart healthcare. The era of plain classical classroom trainings is over. Our time is the era of adaptable e-learning for continuous medical education, which allows the entire staff to gain the same level of knowledge directly at their place of work and enables every member to deliver the smart healthcare – the safe, effective and high-quality patient care. Continuous education with e-learning can help keep learners' interest and motivation up because the learning units can be enhanced with videos or interactive elements (<https://healthmanagement.org>). When it comes to learning and information needs, medical professionals will first turn to the online medical platforms – providing the content is valuable and up to date. Continuous education with e-learning can help keep learners' interest and motivation up because the learning units can be en-

hanced with videos or interactive elements. E-learning is more efficient in most cases because learners gain knowledge, skills, and attitudes faster than through traditional instructor-based methods – translating into improved motivation and performance. With reference to INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme, the aim was to obtain information about the learning resources available, to identify the needs and to match them with the resources (<https://www.cep.si/d-care-labs>, <https://www.interreg-danube.eu>). It realizes by defining the needs for tools and methods for the collaborative and inclusive learning process, attitudes towards e-learning and user acceptance criteria. An example of the individual learning process may be the training of older adults in the use of a fall detection device that sends alarms to the caregiver in the event of a fall. At the organizational level, an example is the training of caregivers in the care unit in the use of an intelligent paperless health management system.

2. Data and Methodology. According to the design of the project the following participants should be included: research and education staff, health and social care providers, informal caretakers, civil society, public administration, economic agents (<https://www.interreg-danube.eu>, <https://www.cep.si/d-care-labs>). Targeted groups for smart care in Danube region – Republic of Moldova: oncological patients, persons over 55 years of age. An efficient innovation is realized due to cooperative partnerships – triple- and quadruple-helix clusters, which stimulate innovative activity through the intensive interaction. The following potential means will be used within the innovation process: the infrastructure for enabling the development of innovation and knowledge transfer, the knowledge networks and collaboration platforms for supporting continuous improvement, continuous education and training programs for health professionals and other stakeholders working with age-friendly smart care and health care solutions. The development of the Innovative Learning Environments assumes digitization in the field of health – an informational system for monitoring patients in care. The learning content, tools, methodologies and programs are created on a basis of the survey spiral (market demand, trainee demand, etc.) and characteristics of the learner. We performed also the narrative review of the updated bibliographic sources under the form of a synthesis of the primary studies, dedicated to the innovation and learning. In order to realize the aim of the studies, the scientific medical publications were searched via GoogleSearch, PubMed, Z-library, NCIB, Medscape, Hinari database, by the keywords: “smart healthcare”, “oncological patients”, “innovation”, “education”, “triple- and quadruple-helix clusters”, “Innovative Learning Environments”, “digitization”, “management”. We used the following research methods and data collection tools: epidemiological, descriptive, observational, historical, comparative, secondary data analysis (Saha I., Paul B., (2020). Fifteen relevant primary sources were identified and selected, according to the impact score significance, with the scientific, reproducible and transparent approach to the subject under discussion, with the subsequent data extraction, evaluation and interpretation. Intending to minimize errors, a copy of the data extraction sheet was initially created, sharing all the items to be gained from the primary studies.

3. The Model, Findings and Discussion. With reference to INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme, the innovative learning environments are the systemic learning ecosystems built on the principle of open, agile, flexible and dynamic education and training. Innovative learning environments are designed and operated on the basis of the comprehensive involvement of learning actors (trainees, trainers, companies, educational institutions, employment agencies, etc.). Innovative learning environments include educational and management activities, and learning outcomes. While realizing the narrative review of reference sources (<https://www.interreg-danube.eu>, <https://www.cep.si/d-care-labs>), we pointed out the following channels, tools and approaches related to the learning process: books and articles, study reports, workshops, internet and social media, external expertise, international conferences, online courses and webinars, advanced training, in-house training, study visits to other regions (in your country),

study visits to other countries, study visits by other national delegations, study visits by international delegations, practice-based learning (action learning). The innovative networked learning environments are designed in such pathway that can be used to create learning tools, content, and training programs to enhance or develop the skills needed in project regions to provide new integrated care services. The innovative learning pilot programs assume: digital skills for smart care services; digital skills for older patients receiving smart care services; data analysis and monitoring processes for the development and provision of intelligent care services; smart care skills for the provision of social services / health services.

The following potential circumstances and means are identified and should be used for realization of the innovation process in healthcare, including oncology service:

1. Established infrastructure to enable the development of innovation and knowledge transfer, such as living and medical laboratories, demonstrators, test sites, exhibition halls, easily accessible research environments, clinical trials, open source facilities;
2. Established health knowledge networks, collaboration healthcare platforms to support continuous improvement;
3. Established public-private partnerships;
4. Support for bringing medical products and services to patients at home or to the medical supplies market;
5. Continuing education and training programs for health professionals and other stakeholders working with age-friendly smart health care solutions;
6. Procedural and administrative simplifications;
7. Programs for innovation cooperation partnerships;
8. Support for capitalizing on research results;
9. Support on legal issues, including intellectual property rights, procurement, regulations;
10. Support for the involvement of volunteers and volunteer centers.

The implementation of an informational system for monitoring patients in care alleviates and decreases the fear of the elderly cancer patients of loneliness, illness and death. Digital care technology can really help social workers and the families of the elderly patients by remote monitoring of their health through various smart devices, means and tools. The convergence of digital technologies with health, healthcare, the lives of oncological patients would increase the efficiency of healthcare delivery and make medicine more personalized and accurate for each of them.

Telemedicine could allow doctors to recommend treatment to patients in their homes, and the pandemic has shown us how important this is in a time of public health emergencies.

For oncohematological patients, periods of post-chemotherapy discontinuation often require special care to be discussed and monitored with a physician or at least a person with knowledge of oncology, and digitalization in medicine would be a way to ensure the universal right to care medical.

The digitization of medicine in the field of oncology allows: the prevention of post-chemotherapy complications and improvement of the complementarity of health services, support of research and development in the field of smart health in the Republic of Moldova; the prevention of concomitant pathologies and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle, by improving the quality of life of citizens and preparing the ground for more efficient ways of organizing and providing healthcare services. The implementation of smart healthcare for elderly oncological patients in the Republic of Moldova is a radical change, which may consist of the following: shift of the medical model – from disease-centred care to patient-centred care; shift of the construction of informatization – from clinical informatization to regional medical informatization, which would involve all ecosystems; shift of the medical management – from general management to personalized management; shift of the concept of prevention and treatment of cancer patients – from the focus on the disease treatment to the focus on preventive care (Tian S et al, 2019, Liu B.H. et al., 2018).

The traditional model of hospital-centred health management seems to be less capable to adequately cope with the growing number of patients and diseases. The new model of health management within the frame of smart healthcare pays more attention to the patient self-management. It emphasizes real-time self-monitoring of patients, immediate feedback of health data and timely intervention of medical staff. Smart care focuses on meeting the individual needs of cancer patients, while improving the efficiency of health care, which greatly enhances the experience of medical and health services, and is the direction of future development of modern medicine. The implementation and function of smart healthcare may be divided as follows, taken into consideration different needs: assisting diagnosis and treatment, health management, disease prevention and risk monitoring, virtual assistants, assisting drug research, smart hospitals (Tian S et al, 2019, Martin J.L. et al, 2010, Estrin D., Sim I., 2010, Gagnon M.P. et al, 2016, Redfern J., 2017).

Smart hospitals rely on information and communication technology-based environments, especially those based on internet of things optimization and automated processes, to improve existing patient care procedures and introduce new features (Zhang J.Z. et al., 2018). There are three main types of services for smart hospitals: services for medical staff, services for patients, and services for administrators. The demands of these service users must be considered in hospital management decisions. In hospital management, the information platform that integrates multiple digital systems based on internet of things connects digital devices, intelligent buildings, and personnel.

Informational technology and modern biotechnology are the cornerstones of smart healthcare. These technologies are widely used in all aspects of smart healthcare. With the application of technologies such as artificial intelligence, surgical robots, and mixed reality, the diagnosis and treatment of diseases has become more intelligent. Using artificial intelligence to built the clinical decision support system, it has achieved certain results, such as the diagnosis of lung cancer and skin cancer (Polat K., Gunes S., 2008, Esteva A. et al., 2017). The accuracy of artificial intelligence diagnosis results exceeds that of human doctors. 6–8 Machine learning-based systems are quite often even more accurate than experienced physicians, especially in pathology and imaging. While performing the narrative review and analysis of the bibliographic sources, we have identified several groups of smart healthcare options, which may be efficiently used in oncology service from the Republic of Moldova. From patient's prospects, they can use portable devices to monitor their health at any time, require medical assistance through virtual nurses, and implement remote services. From a physician's prospects, a variety of intelligent clinical decision support systems are used to help and improve diagnosis. Physicians can manage medical information through an integrated information platform that includes Laboratory Information Management System, Picture Archiving and Communication Systems, and last but not least the Electronic Medical Records. From the prospects of scientific research institutions, it is possible to use techniques such as machine learning instead of manual drug screening and to find suitable subjects using big data (Tian S et al, 2019, Pan F., 2019). This would reduce the risks associated with, and caused by the disease, while facilitating medical institutions to monitor the prognosis of the disease.

By using technologies, smart healthcare can effectively reduce the costs and risks of medical procedures, improve the efficiency of medical resources usage, promote exchanges and cooperation in different regions, foster the development of telemedicine and self-care.

Conclusions. Smart healthcare system is an organic complex that involves multiple dimensions, including disease prevention and monitoring, diagnosis and treatment, intelligent hospital management and health decision-making, innovative learning and medical researches.

Smart healthcare in oncology can facilitate better self-management of health and reduce costs of medical services.

Smart healthcare may achieve unified management of medical materials and information.

Smart healthcare reduces research time, costs and improves the overall research efficiency.

References:

1. Tian, S., Yang, W., Le Grange, J.M. et al. (2019). Smart healthcare: making medical care more intelligent. *Global Health Journal*, 3 (3), 62-65.
2. Martin, J.L., Varilly, H., Cohn, J., Wightwick, G.R. (2010). Preface: technologies for a smarter planet. *IBM J Res Dev*, 2010,54 (4):1-2.
3. Gagnon, M.P., Ngangue, P., Payne-Gagnon J., Desmartis, M. (2016). m-Health adoption by healthcare professionals: a systematic review. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*, 23 (1): 212-220.
4. Redfern, J. (2017). Smart health and innovation: facilitating health-related behaviour change. *Proc Nutr Soc*, 76 (3): 328-332.
5. Kelly, C.J., Young, A.J. (2017). Promoting innovation in healthcare. *Future Healthcare Journal*, 4 (2), 121-125.
6. <https://www.interreg-danube.eu>. D-CARELABS. Developing Labs to Facilitate Home Care Innovation and Entrepreneurship in the Danube Region.
7. <https://www.cep.si/d-care-labs>. INTERREG Danube Transnational Programme. D-CARE LABS.
8. Saha, I., Paul, B. (2020). Essentials of biostatistics & research methodology - 3rd edition. Academic Publishers, Kolkata, 1-398.
9. Liu, BH, He, KL, Zhi, G. (2018). The impact of big data and artificial intelligence on the future medical model. *Med Philos*, 39 (22), 1-4.
10. Estrin, D, Sim, I. (2010). Open mHealth architecture: an engine for health care innovation. *Science*, 330 (6005): 759-760.
11. Zhang, J.Z., Li, Y.K., Cao, L.Y., Zhang, Y. (2018). Research on the construction of smart hospitals at home and abroad. *Chin Hos Manag*, 38 (12): 64-66.
12. Polat, K, Gunes, S. (2008). Principles component analysis, fuzzy weighting pre-processing and artificial immune recognition system based diagnostic system for diagnosis of lung cancer. *Expert Syst Appl*, 34(1), 214-21.
13. Esteva, A., Kuprel, B., Novo, A R.A., et al. (2017). Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks. *Nature*, 542 (7638): 115-118.
14. Pan, F. (2019). Health care is an area where information technology plays an important role: an interview with Wu He-Quan, member of the Chinese Academy of Engineering. *China Med Herald*, 16 (3): 1-3.
15. <https://healthmanagement.org/pdf/article/the-importance-of-continuous-education-in-healthcare>. HealthManagement.org Promoting Management and Leadership. Volume 17 - Issue 2, 2017 - Special Edition on e-Learning. The Importance of Continuous Education in Healthcare.